

Image-To-Image Translation Network Model Development for Automatic Contrast Enhancement on Low-Dose Mammographic Images

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Abstract: *This study presents an Image-to-Image neural network model designed to enhance the contrast of low-dose mammographic images, aiming to improve diagnostic quality while adhering to the ALARA principle. Using a dataset of breast phantom images acquired at varying radiation doses, the model leverages generative adversarial networks (GANs) to reconstruct high-contrast images from low-dose scans. Performance evaluation based on structural similarity (SSIM) and Carneiro Contrast Index (CCI) demonstrates that the model effectively approximates high-dose image quality, supporting its potential role in reducing radiation exposure without compromising diagnostic accuracy.—*

Keywords: *2D Mammogram, Artificial Intelligence, Breast Cancer, Image Contrast, Neural Networks —*

I. INTRODUCTION

After decades of scientific improvement of women's health medicine, breast cancer is still known to be the most common one among females worldwide. According to the World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF), in 2022, 2.296.840 new cases and 666.103 deaths were registered [1]. In this context, the mammographic exam is considered the gold standard exam for early breast cancer detection, as it is capable of detecting lesions before they become palpable [2].

In terms of the production of the radiographic images, the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Possible) Principle [3] [4] is currently used to help healthcare professionals to guide the radiation amount received by the patient during the exam acquisition, aiming to balance safe radiation levels and image quality. While low radiation acquisitions are safer for the patient and more financially sustainable for hospitals, the contrast levels achieved are not sufficient to differentiate similar breast structures, such as fibroglandular tissue and lesions, preventing proper image analysis and diagnosis. However, high radiation acquisitions, which lead to great contrast levels, can be unsafe for all people involved in the exam, such as technicians and patients [5].

In this scenario, Artificial Intelligence systems, such as neural networks, are often used to develop trustable solutions in healthcare, especially for their capacity of processing great amounts of data without being influenced by human error factors [6].

As a way to overcome the duality presented by the ALARA Principle, the present study aims to propose, discuss, and validate the usage of Image-To-Image neural network models for reconstructing low-dose mammographic images with high-dose acquisition contrast, allowing physicians to have, by exposing patients to the least radiation possible, reliable and high contrast quality exams.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The initial dataset [7] contained 35 8-bits DICOM images of a clinically validated breast phantom, acquired on a *GE Senographe Essential* mammograph. During the acquisitions, 12 different fat-tissue arrangements were established, out of which 11 had their mammographic images acquired in 3 different settings: low-dose (group A), with 3.359 mGy of average entrance dose and 0.980 mGy of average organ dose; automatic dose (group B), with an average entrance dose of 8.407 mGy and 1.835 mGy of average organ dose; and high-dose (group C), with an average entrance dose of 11.523 mGy and an average organ dose of 2.568 mGy. Once the remaining arrangement only presented group A and group B acquisitions, it was excluded from the analysis.

The filtered dataset resulted in a total of 33 images, being one from group A, one from group B, and one from group C, for each of the 11 remaining arrangements. For better standardization of the network input, and aiming peak performance levels, all the group B (automatic dose) images were discarded, totalizing 22 images. Figure 1 graphically represent the final dataset.

Fig. 1. Example of different entrance dose acquisitions for the same phantom configuration. (a) Low-dose acquisition; (b) Automatic dose acquisition; (c) High-dose acquisition;

B. Data Pre-Processing

Before submitting the data into the network, a data augmentation protocol was established. All the images were submitted to an authorial patch-extraction Python script, that cropped them into 150x150 sized patches and transformed them to PNG format, resulting, after the exclusion of the patches that displayed mainly the black X-Ray background, in 1504 patches, being 752 from group A and 752 from group C.

After the patching process was complete, the correspondent images in group A and group C were merged side by side in order to satisfy the input expected by the network, as shown in Figure 2. Out of the resulting 752 pairs, 25% (or 188 pairs) was randomly sorted in order to compose the testing dataset, while the remaining 75% (or 564 pairs) composed the training dataset.

Fig. 2. Input-Output pair example.

C. Image-to-Image Network Model

For this study, a trained network model was chosen [8] [9], and the required adaptations were made to better address the main goal. The Image-to-Image model was considered to be the most viable option for its high capacity to learn patterns and similarities from an input-output pair of images.

In this case, input corresponded to low-dose data and the output corresponded to high-dose data. The Generative Adversial Network (GAN) [10] featured on the Image-To-Image approach, learns through a convolutional analysis patterns and similarities between the low-dose and high-dose version of the dataset, in order to learn ways to do the transform. Meanwhile, the Discriminative Network,

also featured on the model, receives the generated high-dose images from the GAN and tries to tell them apart from the original high-dose images, helping the generative system to improve based on its real-time feedback.

Different training parameters were tested, aiming to evaluate the model's behavior on a medical image context, since it is not what it was first designed to.

D. Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM)

The Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) was chosen as the main performance metric for the generated results, once it is consistently validated on the medical imaging field [11], and known to present great consistency with image analysis made by human specialists such as radiologists.

In the present study, the SSIM was used to compare the structural similarity between the real high-dose breast images with the ones generated by the neural network.

E. Carneiro Contrast Index (CCI)

The Carneiro Contrast Index [12] (originally *Índice Carneiro de Contraste*) was set as a secondary performance metric. It consists on a global contrast index, based on a 3x3 spatial filter, first created and validated for 12-bit Breast Tomosynthesis images, that returns a single value representing the average standard deviation found by the filter's iterations.

After normalizing the target image, the 3x3 sized kernel scrolls through the matrix, replacing each pixel for its standard deviation compared to its full neighborhood. For the pixels placed on the edges of the image, the missing pixels in the kernel are replaced by its mirrored position pixels on the matrix, in order to avoid outlier values.

Once the standard deviation matrix is set, its mean value determines the final CCI index. For group A (low-dose) images, the average CCI value was 1.995, as for group C (high-dose), the average CCI was 7.410, confirming the contrast-dose relation hypothesis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Once the dataset was fully prepared to be received by the network, different training parameters were chosen to be evaluated: Number of epochs, initialization function, number of GAN filters, and GAN mode.

As a starting point, in the initial training of the network, the default parameters were used, and further alterations were made based on its results. Table 1 represents the parameters used for each training.

	EPOCHS	INIT	GAN FILTERS	GAN MODE
V0	200	normal	64	vanilla
V1	600	xavier	64	vanilla
V2	500	xavier	96	lsgan
V3	200	orthogonal	96	wgangp

TABLE 1. Training parameters for each training version.

The results obtained by the SSIM analysis, shown in Table 2, indicate a better structural similarity on versions 0 and 3, which suggests that the GAN mode used in version 2, 'vanilla', may not be appropriate to achieve the aimed results. In addition, both of the better performing results were trained on a low number of epochs, demonstrating the model's ease to converge.

COMPARED GROUP	MEAN	MIN	MAX	STDV
HIGH DOSE - V0	0,8579	0,4902	0,9181	0,0974
HIGH DOSE - V1	0,8270	0,5234	0,9094	0,0988
HIGH DOSE - V2	0,8240	0,5207	0,9059	0,0859
HIGH DOSE - V3	0,8550	0,5361	0,8910	0,0954

TABLE 2. Statistical SSIM analysis for each training version, considering the original high-dose patches as reference.

The CCI analysis for the original dataset and the reconstructed images, shown in Table 3, expands the hypothesis established by the SSIM conclusions, indicating that, in terms of global contrast, versions 1 and 2 better approach the CCI results in the original dataset. This may suggest that on both CCI best performing versions, the network might tend to make up fake pixels information to compensate the lack of structural similarity one it goes through the discriminator's analysis.

IMAGE GROUP	MEAN	MAX	MIN	STDV
A - ORIGINAL	0,8600	0,4411	1,1590	0,1455
B - ORIGINAL	1,1724	0,6615	1,6235	0,1977
B - V0	0,9302	0,6590	1,1588	0,1035
B - V1	1,1444	0,6853	1,3620	0,1723
B - V2	1,1012	0,7177	1,3943	0,1881
B - V3	1,0170	0,7527	1,1926	0,1226

TABLE 3. Statistical analysis for the CCI results on each training version.

Thus, among the versions that best performed in the SSIM analysis, the 3rd one has shown to be the most balanced in terms of structural learning and contrast distribution, with an average SSIM value of 85.55% and 86.75% or mean CCI . Figure 3 shows the qualitative results obtained on the 3rd version of training.

Fig. 3. Graphic example of the 3rd version results. (a) Column representing original low-dose examples; (b) Column representing original high-dose examples; (c) Column representing the generated high-dose images;

The examples in Figure 4 show a case with high SSIM (E1) and a case with low SSIM (E2), between the versions and the actual high dose image.

		SSIM (E1/E2)	E1	E2
		CCI (E1/E2)		
Low Dose	CCI	0.832 / 0.63		
	SSIM	<u>0.88</u> / 0.49		
High Dose	CCI	1.108 / 0.90		
	CCI	<u>1.18</u> / 0.90		
V0	SSIM	0.86 / 0.452		
	CCI	1.15 / 0.85		
V1	SSIM	0.88 / <u>0.54</u>		
	CCI	1.02 / 0.87		
V2	SSIM	0.86 / 0.452		
	CCI	<u>1.15</u> / 0.85		
V3	SSIM	0.88 / <u>0.54</u>		
	CCI	1.02 / 0.87		

Fig. 4. Visual comparison between the original images and the generated results.

For E1, both V0 and V3 presented SSIM of 0.88, but were V1 and V2 that resulted in CCI (1.18 and 1.15 respectively) even better than the actual high dose CCI image (1.108). Therefore, it should be considered that V1 and V2 also had SSIM close to those of V0 and V3. In addition, in the visual comparison of E1, it is not possible to perceive utilizations of low similarity difference between the results of the versions and the real high dose image.

For E2, the highest SSIM was 0.54 in result V3. The worst SSIM was V2 (0.45) followed by V0 (0.49), showing that for this image, no version had a result with good similarity. However, the CCI of V0 (1.0) exceeded the CCI of the real high-dose image (0.90) and V1 had the same index of the real image, being considered small the difference between the CCI of the versions, showing that the automatic contrast enhancement of the model can be considered quite satisfactory.

Considering that the objective of this study is contrast enhancement so that low dose image has equivalent quality to high dose, CCI shows that this objective is achieved by all versions and more than one example. This can also be proven by the data presented in Table 3.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, the Image-To-Image model presented itself as a promising tool for reconstructing low-dose 2D mammographic images, as well as a potential ally to reinforce the ALARA principle, once it was able to successfully apply a higher contrast reconstruction on the images to which it was presented.

For further studies and development of this proposal, in order to improve the results and the correlation between structural similarity and global contrast enhancement, it is crucial to investigate other training parameters that may enhance even more the network's convergence. Also, more reliable results can be achieved by testing the model on larger datasets, including real breast full images.

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